

EDUCATIONAL POTENTIAL OF WEBTOONS IN TEACHING KOREAN VOCABULARY

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Abstract. *This article examines the potential of using Korean webtoons in the process of teaching Korean vocabulary to school students. Utilizing webtoons as educational material promotes immersion in everyday language, aids in memorizing vocabulary in context, and enhances language comprehension skills. In this context, studying webtoons as a tool for teaching Korean vocabulary is a relevant task, especially considering the needs and interests of modern youth, who favor interactive and visually engaging content.*

Keywords: *webtoons, multimedia resources, motivation, visual content, education, vocabulary, innovation.*

In the modern conditions of globalization and development of information technologies, educational methods and approaches are subject to significant changes. There is a need to adapt the educational process to new digital realities, interests and preferences of modern schoolchildren, which are formed under the influence of Internet culture and multimedia content. In this context, more and more attention is paid to the use of digital resources, such as webtoons, for teaching foreign languages, in particular, the Korean language. [1]

Understanding these concepts is valuable in terms of mastering a foreign language, and therefore in terms of understanding a foreign culture, since mastering a foreign language is, first of all, mastering a new culture. With this approach, language acts as an important component of it and a form of expression of a national view of the world [2]

South Korean culture, as expressed through phenomena such as K-pop, Korean dramas, and webtoons, has a strong influence on young people around the world. Webtoons thus provide a unique platform through which learners can learn Korean in the context of contemporary culture, making vocabulary acquisition much easier and more enjoyable. Korean webtoons are not only a means of entertainment but also a source of authentic vocabulary, phraseology, and cultural characteristics, making them useful for language learning. [3] Webtoons, with their visual appeal, accessibility, and contemporary themes, have a significant influence on young people, helping to popularize the Korean language and culture.

Webtoon (Korean: 웹툰) – from the English “webtoon” – a combination of the words “web” – “Internet” and “cartoon” – “cartoon, comic book” – is a format of digital comics, originally created in South Korea and intended for easy reading on mobile devices. Webtoon can be called manhwa (Korean: 만화) – a term used to describe Korean comics.

Webtoons became possible due to the high level of Internet penetration and availability of mobile devices in South Korea in the early 2000s, which provided the conditions for their mass distribution. Platforms such as Naver Webtoon and Daum Webtoon played a key role in popularizing the new format, offering authors the opportunity to publish their works for free and reach a wide audience. The main audience of webtoons are young users, teenagers and people

under 30 years old who actively use the Internet. Many webtoons are categorized by universal themes such as love, friendship, and self-determination, allowing readers from different cultures to find common ground. This closeness is enhanced by the modern settings that reflect the rhythm of the digital age, which is especially relatable to the younger generation.[4]

With the growing interest in integrating digital technologies into the educational process, webtoons not only help learners develop language skills but also facilitate their immersion in the cultural environment of the target language. The following discussion highlights the main advantages of webtoons in language learning, their pedagogical potential, and their impact on learning effectiveness. [5]

Authenticity of the language environment.

Webtoons provide learners with the opportunity to immerse themselves in an authentic language environment because their language and content reflect the real communication practices of native speakers. They include idioms, colloquialisms, slang, and culturally specific phrases, making them a valuable resource for acquiring a living, dynamic language.

Multimodality and cognitive accessibility.

Webtoons effectively combine text and visual information, which is consistent with the principles of multimodal learning. According to Mayer's cognitive learning theory, visual accompaniment to text facilitates the assimilation of material by reducing cognitive load. Illustrations facilitate an intuitive understanding of new words and grammatical structures, helping students remember them in context.

Developing reading skills and text comprehension.

Reading webtoons promotes the gradual development of text comprehension skills: from recognizing basic vocabulary to analyzing complex narrative structures. The episodic structure of webtoons maintains students' attention, stimulating them to read regularly, and the variety of genres allows you to adapt the materials to the interests and level of each student.

Increased motivation to learn

Motivation is a key factor in success in language learning. Webtoons, with their engaging stories and vivid visuals, arouse learners' interest in the material and make learning an exciting activity. Regularly updated episodes help maintain interest and engagement.

Availability and ease of use

The availability of webtoons through mobile apps and web platforms makes it easy to integrate this tool into a learner's daily life. Learners can use them anytime and anywhere, which is especially important for independent learning.

Cultural Immersion

In addition to language skills, webtoons convey a rich cultural context. They introduce students to the traditions, daily life, and worldview of native speakers. Cultural aspects presented through illustrations and stories make learning more profound and multifaceted.

In this way, webtoons are an effective tool for teaching Korean vocabulary, combining entertainment, education, and cultural functions. To integrate them into the educational process, it is recommended to use webtoons as an additional resource for independent vocabulary learning, as well as include them in classroom lessons for analyzing language structures and discussing stories in groups. Their multimedia format, genre diversity, and cultural content make webtoons a popular and adaptable resource for educational purposes. Webtoons help to develop interest in the

Korean language and culture, facilitating the learning process and offering unique opportunities for pedagogical application.

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